

PERCOLATED NETWORK OF BIOCARBON IN A BLEND OF NYLON 6 AND POLYPROPYLENE

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ABSTRACT

The sustainable filler biocarbon was added into nylon-6/polypropylene blends, where the composites were successfully prepared by melt extrusion. The influence of the biocarbon content and size on the morphology and properties of these composites were evaluated. Using scanning electrical microscopy (SEM), it was found that the biocarbon was primarily distributed in the nylon-6 phase due to the similar polarity of the biocarbon. Therefore, the selective distribution of biocarbon greatly influenced the morphology and properties of these formulations. Results indicated that the high loading of biocarbon in the nylon-6 phase resulted in a decreased coefficient linear of thermal expansion (CLTE) and increased viscosity of the nylon-6/polypropylene blends.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polypropylene (PP) is a commodity polymer widely used in the automotive industry due to its high hydrophobicity, ease of processing, low density, and competitive cost, etc. (1). Polyamide 6 (PA6) is an engineering polymer found in applications such as transportation, sport equipment, clothing, etc. applied neat, in blends or in composites. It is characterized by high strength, chemical resistance, and ease of coloring (2). Mixing PP with PA6 allows enhancement of additional aspects of PA6 such as hydrophobicity, material toughness and density reduction. The mixtures of PA6 with PP are known to result in immiscible blends as a result of their difference in polarity (3).

Biocarbon, also called biochar, is obtained from the pyrolysis of biomass and waste, as well as two other fractions: syngas and bio-oil (4). Biocarbon is a solid porous residue whose properties are highly dependent on the source of biomass used, the thermal treatment applied, etc., so far it is mainly used for applications in agriculture as a soil amendment. It has recently gained interest in the plastic industry for its reinforcement effects. Polypropylene mixed with biocarbon has revealed a low interfacial interaction attributed to their difference in polarity; the use of a compatibilizer or rubber was shown as good strategies to improve the interface and as a result the performance of the inherent composites (5). Polyamide 6 when compounded with biocarbon showed a good interaction, especially with biocarbon prepared at low temperature, and resulting in higher mechanical properties (6). This change was attributed to the higher amount of remnant functional groups on the biocarbon when subjected to lower heating temperatures.

The addition of filler in a polymer matrix can result in the percolation of particles, which is observed usually at very high loadings. The influence of the particle shape, size, as well as the polymer viscosity, etc., are many parameters investigated to understand how to tailor this specific property (7). Composites with such morphology have already been found in commercial applications for their enhanced reinforcing effect, thermal conductivity,

etc. as for instance in tires. A complementary strategy consists of adding the filler in a blend of immiscible polymers with one polymer having a higher affinity for the filler. This way the migration of the filler in the dispersed phase can generally reduce the amount of filler used, and eventually reduce the price of the final material. Obviously other types of morphologies can be expected where the filler is located at the polymers interface, or in the matrix.

This research aims to better understand the effect of biocarbon size and content on the morphology when compounded with PA6 and PP in the absence of any compatibilizer or ternary polymeric phase.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The polypropylene used is 1120H supplied by Pinnacle Polymers with a melting point at 165 °C, and polyamide 6 (PA6) B27E used is a product from BASF and has a melting point at 220 °C. Miscanthus, provided by Competitive Green Technologies, Leamington, Ontario, Canada, was pyrolyzed at 350 °C for 30 minutes in a nitrogen environment before ball milling for 2 hours at 200 rpm.

The composites were fabricated in one-step method using a DSM Xplore (Xplore) at 250°C and 100 rpm for 2 minutes with PA6/PP 20/80 and biocarbon loadings at 0, 10 and 40 wt.%. The following analyses were performed on the strands obtained after compounding.

A thermomechanical analysis (TMA) was used to measure the coefficient linear of thermal expansion (CLTE) using a TMA 2940 (TA Instruments) in nitrogen atmosphere. The experiments were conducted at 3 °C/min on a broad temperature range: from -40 °C to 150 °C. Two specimens were tested for every sample.

The particles morphology was analyzed and the phases dispersion were observed after cryo-fracture of the samples, by scanning electron microscopy (Phenom ProX).

The rheology was measured on a MCR302 rheometer from Anton Paar, in oscillatory detection mode at 250°C under nitrogen flow from 0.1 to 700 rad/s and 0.1% strain.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: CLTE measured in both the glassy (black) and the rubbery (red) state for the neat polymers and biocarbon composites with different ball milling time.

Fig.1. shows the effect of adding biocarbon on the value of coefficient linear of thermal expansion (CLTE), as compared to the neat polymers. Two ranges of temperature were investigated, above and below the glass transition temperature. The thermal expansion above the glass transition of both PA6 and PP is significantly higher due to the increased molecular motions. In addition, regardless of the range of temperature, the addition of 25 wt.% biocarbon induces a significant decrease of the CLTE.

In complement, the size of the particles was measured. Hammer milled biocarbon particles were characterized to an average particle size of 7 μm while after 4h of ball milling the average particle size dropped to 1.7 μm (8). Therefore, it appears that a longer ball milling time, produces a smaller particle size further decreasing the CLTE (9). For the rest of this study an intermediate ball milling of 2h was used in order to be energy and cost efficient.

Figure 1: SEM of A) biocarbon particles (4000x), B) PA6/PP with 10 wt.% biocarbon, C) PA6/PP with 40 wt.% biocarbon (5000x).

Fig.2A. shows the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the biocarbon powder, highlighting angular and polydispersed particles. When compounded with PA6/PP (Fig.2B. and C.) the biocarbon particles always migrated into the PA6 dispersed phase. For PA6/PP 20/80 loaded at 10 wt.%, a droplet morphology can be observed. For higher loadings, the PA6 droplets deformed, covering the biocarbon particles, and forming a network inside the composite.

Figure 3 Viscoelastic behavior of the composites measured by rheometer: A) Viscosity versus shear stress, and B) shear stress versus shear rate.

Fig.3. shows the viscoelastic behavior of the composites, as compared to the blend, measured in the melt state. The addition of biocarbon particles significantly increases the viscosity of the composites, especially when a

particle network was formed. Similarly, a rise of the yield stress was observed confirming the formation of a 3-dimensional network within the material.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Smaller biocarbon particles are beneficial in reducing the CLTE of composite materials. The biocarbon particles showed a higher affinity for the PA6 polar phase in comparison to the non-polar PP. This resulted in higher particle loading, the deformation of the PA6 dispersed phase fitting the network formed by biocarbon particles. At high loading, the biocarbon particles result in an increase of the viscosity and yield stress.

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